

Examining Learners' Satisfaction with a Values Enhancement Program in Higher Education

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Abstract. Values education is a fundamental component of holistic learner development, fostering ethical behavior, social responsibility, character formation, and personal growth. In higher education, values-oriented programs help prepare learners not only for academic and professional success but also for responsible citizenship and moral decision-making. Although values education has been widely examined in relation to curriculum implementation and character development, few empirical studies have investigated learners' satisfaction with institutionally initiated values-enhancement programs in higher education. This gap limits understanding of how tertiary learners perceive the quality and effectiveness of structured values-formation initiatives. This study examined learners' satisfaction with a Values Enhancement Program (VEP) implemented in a private higher education institution in Bulacan, Philippines. Specifically, it assessed satisfaction in terms of learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and learning experience. A descriptive-survey research design was employed, involving 293 learners who participated in the program. Data were collected using a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The instrument underwent content validation by five experts, obtaining a validity rating of 92%, and demonstrated excellent reliability with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.92. Findings revealed that learners were generally satisfied with the Values Enhancement Program, indicating positive perceptions across all dimensions. Among the four dimensions, learning delivery obtained the highest rating, highlighting the importance of facilitator guidance, instructional clarity, and engagement strategies in enhancing learner satisfaction. Learning materials received the lowest rating, though still satisfactory, suggesting the need for more diverse and enriched instructional resources. The findings emphasize the importance of continuous program evaluation in strengthening values formation initiatives in higher education.

Keywords: Higher Education; Learner Satisfaction; Program Evaluation; Program Improvement; Values Education

Introduction

Higher education institutions are tasked not only with developing academic competence but also with fostering learners' moral, ethical, and social development. In increasingly complex social and technological environments, educational institutions are expected to cultivate responsible citizenship, ethical behavior, empathy, and sound decision-making among learners. Consequently, values education has become an essential component of holistic learner development, emphasizing character formation, moral reasoning, and social responsibility (Lyn, 2023). Scholars argue that values education enables learners to make informed decisions, demonstrate empathy, and contribute positively to society (Papadopoulos et al., as cited in Kilag et al., 2023; Chuen & Yusof, 2021). Moreover, values-oriented learning promotes the integration of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions necessary for ethical and socially responsible action (Alcavar et al., 2021; Cathrin et al., 2021).

The importance of values education is reinforced by international and regional educational frameworks. The United Nations and UNESCO emphasize education's role in promoting human dignity, peace, global citizenship, and social cohesion through initiatives such as Sustainable Development Goal 4 and Global Citizenship Education (Pacho, 2021). Similarly, the ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community Blueprint promotes values related to social harmony, cultural respect, and shared responsibility (ASEAN, 2023). These frameworks

collectively affirm that values education is critical in preparing learners to navigate increasingly interconnected societies.

In the Philippines, values education is deeply embedded in national educational policy. The 1987 Philippine Constitution emphasizes moral character formation and civic responsibility as essential to nation-building (Department of Education, 2022). This commitment is reflected in curricular initiatives such as *Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao* under the K–12 Program and, more recently, the MATATAG Curriculum, which integrates peace education, conflict resolution, and Good Manners and Right Conduct (GMRC) with twenty-first-century competencies (Manglicmot, 2024; Presidential Communications Office, 2023). Despite these policy efforts, behavioral concerns among learners remain evident. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022 reported that Filipino learners experience bullying at rates significantly higher than the OECD average, highlighting persistent concerns regarding school climate, learner well-being, and social behavior (OECD, 2023).

In response, many educational institutions have developed school-based values formation initiatives aligned with their mission, vision, and core values to strengthen character development and ethical behavior (SEAMEO, n.d.; Tabora, 2021). One such initiative is the Values Enhancement Program (VEP) implemented in a private higher education institution in Bulacan. Established in 2016, the program integrates values instruction, reflective activities, participatory discussions, and course-based reinforcement to promote personal growth, ethical awareness, and responsible behavior among learners (Richwell Colleges, n.d.).

Although values education has been widely studied in terms of policy implementation, curriculum integration, and character development, limited empirical research has examined learners' satisfaction with institutionally initiated values enhancement programs in higher education settings. Existing studies predominantly focus on elementary and secondary education, leaving a gap in understanding how tertiary learners perceive the quality and effectiveness of structured values formation initiatives (Tabora, 2021; SEAMEO, n.d.). This gap is significant because learner satisfaction serves as an important indicator of program quality, reflecting participants' experiences with instructional materials, learning environments, teaching practices, and overall learning experiences (Espinosa & Gonzales, 2022; Olaya, 2024). Without such evidence, institutions may lack sufficient basis for improving the design and delivery of values formation programs.

This study examined learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program implemented in a private higher education institution in Bulacan. Specifically, it assessed learners' satisfaction in terms of learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and learning experience. The study aimed to generate empirical evidence that may inform program enhancement and contribute to the growing literature on values education in higher education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the learners' level of satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program implemented in a private higher education institution.

Specifically, the study aims to address the following questions;

1. What is the level of learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program in terms of:
 - 1.1 Learning Materials,
 - 1.2 Learning Environment,
 - 1.3 Learning Delivery, and
 - 1.4 Learning Experience?
2. What is the overall level of learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program?
3. Which dimension of the Values Enhancement Program contributes most positively to learners' satisfaction, and presents the greatest opportunity for improvement?
4. Based on the findings, what program enhancement initiatives may be proposed to further strengthen the implementation of the Values Enhancement Program?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on examining learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program (VEP) implemented in a private higher education institution in Bulacan. Specifically, the study assessed learners' satisfaction in terms of learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and learning experience. The respondents consisted of 293 learners who participated in the Values Enhancement Program during the academic year in which the study was conducted. The investigation was limited to measuring learners' satisfaction as reflected in their perceptions and experiences of the program. The study did not examine actual learning outcomes, behavioral changes, academic performance, or long-term impacts of the program. Furthermore, the findings are limited to the participants and institutional context of the study and may not be generalized to other educational institutions without consideration of contextual differences.

Literature Review

Values Education and Holistic Learner Development

Values education is widely recognized as a central component of holistic education because it extends learning beyond academic achievement to include moral, ethical, emotional, and social development. Existing literature consistently supports its role in shaping learners' character and responsible citizenship. Papadopoulos et al., as cited in Kilag et al. (2023), argued that values education equips learners with competencies for informed decision-making, empathy, and positive social participation. Similarly, Chuen and Yusof (2021) emphasized that values formation integrates the cognitive, affective, and behavioral domains, suggesting that values education is most effective when learners not only understand values conceptually but also internalize and practice them. Although scholars generally agree on the importance of values education, differences emerge in how its outcomes are conceptualized. Alcavar et al. (2021) focused on ethical understanding and moral reasoning, while Cathrin et al. (2021) emphasized care, empathy, and socially responsive action. This suggests that values education is multidimensional, involving both internal character formation and external behavioral expression. However, much of the existing literature focuses on theoretical and curricular discussions rather than empirical evaluation of how learners experience values-based interventions. This creates a gap in understanding whether institutional values programs are perceived as meaningful and effective by learners themselves.

Learner Satisfaction in Educational Programs

Learner satisfaction is widely regarded as an important indicator of educational quality and program effectiveness because it reflects learners' perceptions of instructional processes, support systems, and overall educational experiences. Studies suggest that positive learner satisfaction is associated with higher motivation, participation, engagement, and personal development (Espinosa & Gonzales, 2022). In this sense, satisfaction serves not only as a measure of learner perception but also as an indirect indicator of program effectiveness. However, learner satisfaction is a complex construct influenced by multiple dimensions rather than a single factor. Existing research identifies instructional materials, learning environment, instructional delivery, and learning experience as major determinants of satisfaction. While these dimensions are often studied independently, evidence suggests that they interact dynamically in shaping learners' overall educational experience. This implies that satisfaction in values education programs may depend not only on content but also on how the program is delivered and experienced.

Learning Materials

Instructional materials play a critical role in supporting comprehension, engagement, and meaningful participation. Escultor and Moises (2022) highlighted that accessible and innovative learning resources improve learner engagement, particularly in programs involving values formation where contextualized examples and reflective prompts are necessary. Their findings suggest that well-designed materials can enhance learner participation by making abstract values more relatable and applicable. However, the literature also points to persistent challenges. Mista et al. (2024) found that insufficient or limited instructional materials can hinder program effectiveness, particularly in experiential and reflective learning activities. The contrast between these findings suggests that the value of instructional materials lies not merely in their availability but in their adequacy, relevance, and diversity. In values education, this becomes especially important because meaningful internalization often requires varied resources such as case studies, scenarios, multimedia content, and reflective tools.

Learning Environment

A supportive learning environment is consistently identified as a significant contributor to learner engagement and satisfaction. Wong et al. (2021) found that collaborative environments enhance values development by encouraging dialogue, reflection, and shared understanding. Such interaction allows learners to negotiate perspectives and develop social awareness, which are critical in values education. Similarly, Olaya (2024) emphasized that positive school climates promote both academic engagement and personal development. While both studies support the importance of the learning environment, they differ in emphasis: Wong et al. focused on peer collaboration, whereas Olaya highlighted broader institutional climate. This distinction suggests that learner satisfaction in values education is shaped by both micro-level interactions (peer collaboration) and macro-level environmental factors (school culture, safety, openness). Despite this, existing studies rarely examine how these environmental dimensions specifically influence satisfaction in higher education values programs.

Learning Delivery

Instructional delivery remains one of the strongest determinants of learner satisfaction. Brown et al. (2020) and Hart (2021) found that facilitator guidance, clarity of instruction, and meaningful interactions significantly influence learner engagement and educational outcomes. Their findings indicate that facilitators play a particularly important role in values education because values are often transmitted not only through instruction but also through modeling, dialogue, and guided reflection. However, effective delivery involves more than instructional clarity. Studies suggest that pacing, consistency, and facilitator authenticity also influence learner perceptions. This indicates that values education is highly relational; learners respond not only to what is taught but also to how facilitators embody the values being taught. Despite the recognized importance of delivery, empirical studies assessing this dimension within institution-specific values enhancement programs remain limited.

Learning Experience

Meaningful learning experiences contribute significantly to learners' personal growth and values formation. Gomez (2021), Hermawan and Kusniasari (2023), and Yuliana et al. (2025) found that experiential and reflective learning opportunities enhance emotional, social, and moral development. These studies collectively suggest that values are more effectively internalized when learners actively engage in reflection and real-life application rather than passive content consumption. Although these studies consistently support experiential learning, they also imply that meaningful learning experiences require intentional instructional design. Reflection, discussion, and contextual application must be deliberately structured to facilitate deeper internalization of values. This indicates that positive learning experiences in values education are not incidental but are shaped by carefully designed educational interactions.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-survey research design to determine the level of learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program implemented by a private higher education institution. Specifically, the study examined learners' perceptions regarding the program's learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and overall learning experience. Descriptive-survey research is appropriate for studies that seek to systematically gather, describe, and interpret information about existing conditions, attitudes, and experiences of a particular group. Through this approach, researchers are able to obtain firsthand data from respondents and generate a comprehensive understanding of how participants evaluate a given program or phenomenon. The descriptive-survey design facilitates the collection of quantitative data that can be analyzed to identify prevailing trends, patterns, and levels of satisfaction among learners. By employing structured survey instruments, the study captures the perspectives and experiences of participants in an objective and organized manner. This research design is particularly suitable for assessing educational programs because it provides empirical evidence regarding participants' evaluations and perceived effectiveness of program components. In the context of this study, the design enables the researchers to examine the extent to which the Values Enhancement Program meets learners' expectations and contributes to their educational experience. The findings are expected to provide valuable information that may guide institutional administrators and program implementers in enhancing the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of the program.

Sampling Design

The study population consisted of 1,097 fourth-year learners enrolled in a private higher education institution. To estimate the minimum number of participants needed to provide sufficient representation of the target population, Slovin's Formula with a 5% margin of error was used, yielding a required sample size of 293 respondents. The formula was employed solely as a sample size estimation tool to establish the minimum number of respondents needed for quantitative analysis and not as a basis for random respondent selection. Following sample size estimation, purposive sampling was used to identify and recruit eligible participants. This non-probability sampling technique was deemed appropriate because the study required respondents with substantial and sustained exposure to the Values Enhancement Program. Only fourth-year learners were included since they had experienced the program throughout their academic stay and were therefore considered capable of providing informed, comprehensive, and reflective evaluations of its implementation. The use of purposive sampling ensured that data were collected from participants most relevant to the research objectives, particularly in assessing satisfaction across the dimensions of learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and learning experience.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in a private higher education institution located in Plaridel, Bulacan, an institution recognized as the only full-fledged college in the locality that offers academic and training programs approved by the Department of Education (DepEd), the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Through its commitment to quality education and holistic student development, the institution has established itself as a significant provider of educational services in the municipality and neighboring communities. In addition to its academic offerings, the institution has developed a specialized Values Enhancement Program that serves as a distinctive component of its educational framework. This program was conceptualized and personally developed by the institution's founder, reflecting the vision of promoting not only academic excellence but also moral, spiritual, and character formation among learners. The program is designed to cultivate positive values, ethical behavior, and responsible citizenship, thereby contributing to the holistic development of students. Given the central role of the Values Enhancement Program in the institution's educational philosophy, the school provides an appropriate setting for examining learners' satisfaction with the program's learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and overall learning experience.

Research Participants

The participants consisted of 293 out of 1097 fourth-year learners who had participated in the Values Enhancement Program. These learners represented the primary beneficiaries of the program and were considered appropriate respondents for assessing satisfaction with its implementation.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire to assess learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program (VEP). The instrument was developed based on the objectives and components of the program and was designed to measure learners' perceptions of its implementation. The questionnaire consisted of four dimensions: Learning Materials, Learning Environment, Learning Delivery, and Learning Experience. These dimensions were used to evaluate various aspects of the program that contribute to learners' overall satisfaction. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 = Very Dissatisfied, 2 = Dissatisfied, 3 = Moderately Satisfied, 4 = Satisfied, and 5 = Very Satisfied. Higher scores indicated higher levels of satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program. The researcher-made questionnaire underwent content validation by a panel of five experts in educational management, values education, and research methodology. The experts evaluated the instrument in terms of clarity, relevance, appropriateness, and alignment with the objectives of the study. Their recommendations were incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire. Subsequently, pilot testing was conducted, and reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.92, indicating excellent internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, formal approval was obtained from the administration of the private higher education institution to ensure that the research complied with institutional policies and ethical standards. The researchers coordinated with the appropriate school authorities regarding the objectives, scope, and procedures of the study to facilitate the smooth conduct of data collection activities. Upon receiving approval, the researchers identified the target respondents and provided them with a clear explanation of the purpose, significance, and nature of the research. Participants were informed that their involvement in the study was entirely voluntary and that they had the right to decline participation or withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequences. The researchers also assured the respondents that all information collected would be treated with strict confidentiality and would be used solely for academic and research purposes. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the administration of the research instrument to ensure that they fully understood their rights and responsibilities as respondents. Following the consent process, the questionnaires were distributed to the selected participants and adequate time was provided for them to complete the instrument. The researchers remained available to address questions or clarify instructions to ensure accurate and complete responses. After the retrieval of the accomplished questionnaires, the responses were carefully reviewed, encoded, and organized for data processing. The collected data were then subjected to appropriate statistical treatment and analysis to determine the level of learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program in terms of learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and learning experience. The results of the analysis served as the basis for interpreting the findings and formulating conclusions and recommendations relevant to the study.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the level of learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program in terms of Learning Materials, Learning Environment, Learning Delivery, and Learning Experience?

Table 1. Learners' Satisfaction on Values Enhancement Program Learning Materials

Satisfaction - Learning Materials		Ave Rating	Standard Deviation	Description
1.	The instructional materials are clear and well-organized	4.06	0.91	Satisfied
2.	The resources used (books, modules, multimedia) support my understanding of the lessons.	3.98	0.90	Satisfied
3.	The materials provided are sufficient for all learning activities.	3.93	0.87	Satisfied
4.	The material used reflect the values promoted by the institution.	4.07	0.86	Satisfied
5.	The learning resources are accessible and easy to use.	4.08	0.88	Satisfied
Overall		4.02	0.79	Satisfied

As presented in Table 1, learners reported an overall satisfaction level of 4.02 (SD = 0.79), interpreted as Satisfied, indicating that the instructional materials used in the Values Enhancement Program (VEP) were generally perceived positively. Among the indicators, accessibility and ease of use obtained the highest mean score (M = 4.08), suggesting that learners particularly valued materials that were convenient, understandable, and readily available. This finding supports Escultor and Moises (2022), who argued that accessible instructional resources enhance learner engagement by reducing cognitive barriers to participation. In the context of values education, accessibility is especially important because learners must focus not only on understanding content but also on internalizing values through reflection and application. However, the indicator on sufficiency of materials for all learning activities received the lowest rating (M = 3.93), although still within the satisfactory range. This result suggests a gap between resource accessibility and resource adequacy. While learners could access materials easily, the available resources may not have been sufficiently diverse or extensive to support all program activities effectively. This finding aligns with Mista et al. (2024), who observed that limitations in instructional materials often constrain the depth of learner engagement, particularly in programs requiring interactive and reflective activities. From a theoretical perspective, this finding may be interpreted through constructivist learning theory, which posits that learners construct meaning through interaction with varied learning resources and authentic experiences. Values education, unlike purely cognitive instruction, requires exposure to contextualized scenarios, ethical dilemmas, reflective prompts, and experiential activities to promote deeper internalization. The relatively lower rating for material sufficiency may therefore indicate that the program relies more heavily on facilitator-led delivery than on resource-mediated learning. Compared with prior studies, this finding both converges with and extends existing literature. While previous studies emphasize accessibility as a determinant of learner satisfaction (Escultor & Moises, 2022), the present study highlights that access alone is insufficient. For values formation programs, the quality, diversity, and reflective richness of instructional resources are equally critical. Thus, improving material variety may strengthen not only learner satisfaction but also values internalization.

Table 2. Learners' Satisfaction with Values Enhancement Program Learning Environment

Satisfaction - Learning Environment		Ave Rating	Standard Deviation	Description
1.	The classroom setting encourages respect and openness.	4.08	0.90	Satisfied
2.	The environment promotes collaboration among learners.	4.00	0.90	Satisfied
3.	The environment supports reflection during values-related activities.	4.07	0.88	Satisfied
4.	The physical and emotional setting helps me focus on the activities.	4.00	0.89	Satisfied
5.	I am satisfied with how the Values Enhancement Program learning environment encourages active participation in activities.	4.11	0.93	Satisfied
Overall		4.05	0.79	Satisfied

Table 2 shows that learners were satisfied with the learning environment, obtaining an overall mean score of 4.05 (SD = 0.79). The highest-rated indicator was the extent to which the learning environment encouraged active participation (M = 4.11), indicating that learners perceived the VEP as participatory rather than passive. This supports Olaya (2024), who found that positive school climates foster engagement, openness, and learner involvement. In values education, participation is particularly important because moral and ethical understanding develops through dialogue, interaction, and critical reflection rather than one-way instruction. Meanwhile, collaboration among learners and the physical and emotional learning conditions received slightly lower ratings (M = 4.00 each), although both remained satisfactory. These lower ratings suggest that while learners generally felt comfortable and engaged, opportunities for deeper peer interaction and emotionally supportive dialogue could still be enhanced. This finding may be understood through social learning theory (Bandura), which emphasizes that learners acquire values through observation, interaction, and shared experiences. Values are not merely taught; they are socially constructed and reinforced through interpersonal engagement. Thus, collaborative environments play a crucial role in moral development because they provide opportunities to negotiate perspectives, practice empathy, and exercise ethical decision-making. Compared with Wong et al. (2021), who strongly emphasized collaboration as central to civic and values learning, the present findings suggest that collaboration within the VEP may not yet be fully optimized. This indicates that although the program provides a positive atmosphere, its collaborative dimension could be further strengthened through structured peer-sharing, group reflection, and cooperative problem-solving activities. These results imply that a supportive environment in values education extends beyond physical comfort; it includes psychological safety, mutual respect, and meaningful social interaction. Strengthening these elements may deepen both satisfaction and values formation.

Table 3. Learners' Satisfaction on Values Enhancement Program Learning Delivery

Satisfaction - Learning Delivery		Ave Rating	Standard Deviation	Description
1.	The facilitators explain lessons clearly and effectively.	4.12	0.88	Satisfied
2.	The methods used (discussions, reflections, activities) are engaging.	4.10	0.82	Satisfied
3.	The lessons are delivered in an organized and timely manner.	4.03	0.88	Satisfied
4.	The facilitators demonstrate consistency between their teaching and conduct.	4.11	0.89	Satisfied
5.	I am satisfied with the guidance and support provided by facilitators during VEP sessions.	4.17	0.89	Satisfied
Overall		4.10	0.80	Satisfied

As reflected in Table 3, learners expressed a high level of satisfaction with learning delivery, with an overall mean score of 4.10 (SD = 0.80), making this the highest-rated dimension. The highest-rated indicator was facilitator guidance and support (M = 4.17), demonstrating that learners highly value the role of facilitators in the values formation process. This finding is consistent with Hart (2021) and Brown et al. (2020), who emphasized that facilitator engagement significantly enhances learner satisfaction, participation, and moral development. This result carries important theoretical implications. Unlike content-heavy academic subjects, values education is fundamentally relational. Its effectiveness depends not only on curriculum content but also on the credibility, authenticity, and relational competence of facilitators. This supports transformative learning theory, which posits that meaningful learning occurs when facilitators create reflective spaces that challenge assumptions and promote perspective transformation. Interestingly, the indicator on lesson organization and timeliness received the lowest score (M = 4.03). While still satisfactory, this suggests that instructional pacing and session structuring remain areas for improvement. Beruin (2025) similarly identified time management as a common challenge in values education programs, where discussions and reflective processing often require flexible pacing. A critical interpretation of this finding suggests that learners may prioritize relational quality over structural efficiency. In other words, learners may tolerate minor organizational limitations when facilitator support is strong. This highlights an important insight: in values education, how facilitators engage learners may matter more than rigid instructional sequencing. Compared with prior studies, the findings reinforce the consistent importance of facilitator competence across values-oriented programs. More importantly, this study extends the literature by demonstrating that learning delivery is the strongest predictor of satisfaction in an institution-based VEP. This suggests that facilitators function not merely as instructors but as role models who embody the values being taught.

Table 4. Learners' Satisfaction on Values Enhancement Program Learning Experience

Satisfaction - Learning Experience		Ave Rating	Standard Deviation	Description
1.	The activities are relevant to my experiences as a student.	4.03	0.87	Satisfied
2.	The program sessions are meaningful and engaging.	4.06	0.85	Satisfied
3.	The activities allowed adequate time for reflection.	4.02	0.89	Satisfied
4.	The learning experiences is well-structured and organized.	4.03	0.87	Satisfied
5.	I am satisfied with how the VEP learning experiences contribute to my personal growth and values development	4.15	0.89	Satisfied
Overall		4.06	0.79	Satisfied

Table 4 reveals that learners were satisfied with their overall learning experience, with a mean score of 4.06 (SD = 0.79). The highest-rated indicator was the contribution of the program to personal growth and values development (M = 4.15), indicating that learners recognized the program's meaningful influence on their personal formation. This supports Gomez (2021), Hermawan and Kusniasari (2023), and Yuliana et al. (2025), who emphasized that experiential learning and reflective engagement are essential for moral and values development. The lowest-rated indicator was adequacy of reflection time (M = 4.02), suggesting that learners may benefit from more structured opportunities for reflection. This finding is particularly important because reflection is central to values internalization. Without adequate reflective processing, learners may participate actively yet fail to translate experiences into lasting personal meaning. From the lens of experiential learning theory (Kolb), learning becomes transformative only when concrete experience is followed by reflection, conceptualization, and application. Thus, insufficient reflection time may weaken the program's capacity to facilitate deep values integration. Compared with prior literature, this finding introduces an important nuance. While previous studies consistently report positive effects of experiential learning on values formation, the present study suggests that meaningful experiences alone are insufficient unless paired with deliberate reflective processing. This underscores the need to design VEP activities that allocate intentional time for reflection, journaling, and guided dialogue. Overall, the findings suggest that the VEP successfully creates meaningful learning experiences, but stronger reflective mechanisms may further enhance long-term values internalization.

Research Question 2: What is the overall level of learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program?

Table 5: Learners' Satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program

Learners' Satisfaction	Ave Rating	Standard Deviation	Description
Learning Materials	4.02	0.88	Satisfied
Learning Environment	4.05	0.90	Satisfied
Learning Delivery	4.10	0.87	Satisfied
Learning Experience	4.06	0.87	Satisfied
Overall	4.06	0.74	Satisfied

As shown in Table 5, learners reported an overall satisfaction level of 4.06 (SD = 0.74), interpreted as Satisfied, indicating a positive perception of the Values Enhancement Program. All four dimensions received satisfactory ratings, suggesting that the program delivers a generally positive educational experience. Among the dimensions, Learning Delivery obtained the highest rating, while Learning Materials received the lowest. This pattern suggests an important structural dynamic within the program: learner satisfaction appears to be driven more strongly by human interaction and facilitation than by material resources. This finding supports relational models of education, which emphasize the centrality of teacher-learner interaction in shaping educational outcomes. However, as Bates (2021) cautioned, positive satisfaction should not automatically be equated with deep learning or sustained behavioral change. Satisfaction reflects learners' perceptions of program quality, but values education ultimately aims for internalization and behavioral transformation. Thus, while high satisfaction is encouraging, future studies should examine whether these positive perceptions translate into measurable changes in attitudes, behaviors, and ethical decision-making.

Research Question 3: Which dimension of the Values Enhancement Program contributes most positively to learners' satisfaction, and presents the greatest opportunity for improvement?

Learning Delivery contributed most positively to learners' satisfaction, underscoring the importance of facilitator guidance, instructional clarity, and learner engagement. This reinforces the argument of Hart (2021), Brown et al. (2020), and Chuen and Yusof (2021) that effective values education depends heavily on intentional, relational, and well-structured facilitation. In contrast, Learning Materials presented the greatest opportunity for improvement. This indicates that although facilitators effectively sustain engagement, instructional resources may not yet fully support experiential and reflective learning demands. The findings suggest a partial imbalance in program design: human facilitation is highly developed, while material support remains comparatively underdeveloped. Theoretically, this implies that optimal values education requires synergy between instructional delivery, learning resources, environment, and reflective experience. Overreliance on facilitator effectiveness may limit scalability and sustainability. Strengthening learning materials can therefore enhance program resilience and consistency across facilitators and learning contexts.

Research Question 4: Based on the findings, what program enhancement initiatives may be proposed to further strengthen the implementation of the Values Enhancement Program?

Based on the findings, several program enhancement initiatives are proposed to further strengthen the implementation of the Values Enhancement Program. These include improving learning materials by developing more varied, enriched, and sufficient instructional resources, incorporating experiential, case-based, and reflective content to deepen learners' engagement. In addition, strengthening the learning environment is recommended through the promotion of collaborative learning strategies such as group reflection and peer sharing, improvement of classroom conditions that support focus and emotional engagement, and the provision of structured opportunities for learner interaction. The enhancement of learning delivery is also essential, particularly through the provision of facilitator training on pacing, time management, and lesson organization, while reinforcing effective guidance and mentoring practices. Furthermore, the learning experience may be improved by integrating more structured reflective activities, allocating adequate time for processing values-based discussions, and strengthening experiential learning opportunities connected to real-life situations. Lastly, the institutionalization of program monitoring and evaluation is recommended through regular feedback mechanisms to assess learner satisfaction and the utilization of these results for continuous revision and improvement of program content and delivery strategies.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of educational research. Prior to data collection, permission was obtained from the administration of the private higher education institution where the study was conducted. The research protocol was reviewed and approved by the University Research Ethics Committee, ensuring compliance with ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and significance of the research. Informed consent was secured from all participants before they completed the questionnaire. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained throughout the study. No identifying information was collected, and all responses were treated with the utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic and research purposes. Furthermore, participants were assured that their decision to participate or decline participation would not affect their academic standing or relationship with the institution. Data collection was conducted in a respectful and non-coercive manner, upholding the ethical principles of beneficence, respect for persons, and justice.

Conclusion

This study examined learners' satisfaction with the Values Enhancement Program (VEP) implemented in a private higher education institution in Bulacan, focusing on learning materials, learning environment, learning delivery, and learning experience. Findings revealed that learners generally perceived the program positively, indicating that the VEP serves as an effective institutional strategy for supporting holistic learner development, particularly in the personal, social, and moral domains. Among the four dimensions, Learning Delivery emerged as the strongest contributor to learner satisfaction, underscoring the critical role of facilitators in values education. This highlights that effective values formation depends not

only on curriculum content but also on meaningful facilitation, supportive guidance, and authentic educator–learner interactions. Conversely, Learning Materials presented the greatest opportunity for improvement, suggesting the need for more diverse, reflective, and experience-based instructional resources to better support values internalization. The study contributes to the limited literature on learner satisfaction in institution-based values formation programs within higher education. It provides empirical evidence that effective values education requires a balanced integration of strong facilitation, supportive learning environments, quality instructional resources, and structured reflective experiences. While the VEP demonstrates strong potential as a values formation intervention, its long-term impact may be further strengthened through continuous program refinement and future assessment of behavioral and values internalization outcomes.

Recommendations

The findings of the study provide several recommendations to enhance the implementation of the Values Enhancement Program (VEP) and strengthen values education in higher education institutions. First, institutions are encouraged to develop more diverse, sufficient, and enriched instructional materials, including reflective journals, case-based scenarios, multimedia resources, ethical dilemma exercises, and real-life applications to deepen learners' engagement and contextual understanding of values. Second, program implementers should foster a more collaborative and interactive learning environment through activities such as group reflection, peer mentoring, and collaborative problem-solving to enhance social learning and values internalization. Third, continuous professional development for facilitators is essential to improve instructional planning, pacing, time management, and learner engagement strategies, particularly as learning delivery was identified as the strongest contributor to learner satisfaction. Fourth, the program should integrate more structured reflective learning opportunities, such as guided journaling, personal narratives, and facilitated dialogue, allowing sufficient time for learners to process and internalize values-based discussions. Fifth, higher education institutions should institutionalize systematic monitoring and evaluation mechanisms that extend beyond satisfaction surveys, incorporating periodic feedback, outcome-based assessments, and evidence-based program improvements to ensure continuous quality enhancement. Sixth, educational leaders and policymakers are encouraged to strengthen institutional support for values education by embedding structured values formation initiatives within broader student development frameworks, supported by qualified facilitators, adequate resources, and conducive learning environments. Finally, future research should examine the long-term impact of values education programs on behavioral change, ethical decision-making, and values internalization through longitudinal, mixed-method, and comparative studies across institutions, educational levels, and cultural contexts to further advance the field.

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